

Scale Up of Rotating Packed Beds for Solvent Based Carbon Capture

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ABSTRACT

There is a high level of interest in the application of rotating packed beds (RPB) for solvent based post combustion carbon capture. The reason for this is that rotation increases the mass throughput per unit area and causes the liquid to flow in thin films or droplet sprays through the packing thereby increasing the rate of mass transfer. This leads to volume reduction for the absorber in a capture process by a factor of between 15 and 25, with significant reductions, potentially up to 40%, in equipment and installation costs. This technology has been commercialized by two companies, Carbon Clean Solutions and Baker Hughes (formerly Compact Carbon Capture), and interest in studying rotating packed beds for capture and CO₂ utilization has extended to academic institutions around the world.

Figure 1 – Scale up of rotating packed beds, (a) lab scale 80 kg CO₂ capture per day, (b) 1 ton CO₂ capture per day, (c) 10 tons CO₂ capture per day.

A concern for the application of this technology is understanding how to design rotating packed beds to capture of hundreds of tons per day of carbon dioxide from industrial point sources. This

paper describes the scale up of RPB absorbers from lab scale, through 1 ton per day scale to the current 10 tons per day scale as illustrated by Figures 1(a) – (c).

Figure 2(a) shows the gas and solvent flows in an RPB used for carbon capture, and Figure 2(b) shows the parameters that must be estimated to size an RPB. These are, inner diameter (D_i), axial length (z), rotational speed, outer diameter (D_o), power required to drive the RPB (W), and gas pressure drop (ΔP). There are mechanical aspects design mainly focused on rotating seal design which weren't considered in these sizing calculations.

In going from lab scale to 1 ton per day scale the following scale up calculations were completed. The inner diameter was estimated using an equation to prevent liquid entrainment from the amine inlet nozzles (Agarwal 2010), the minimum rotational speed was calculated based on observations of flow patterns in rotating packed beds (Burns 2000), the axial length was calculated using a Wallis type flooding correlation (Lockett 1990) for rotating structured packing, the outer diameter was estimated using data from a lab scale RPB absorber, the work required for rotation was estimated from the change in rotational kinetic energy of the gas and liquid as they flow through the rotating packed bed, and the gas pressure drop was estimated using the equation of motion for gas flow through the RPB with friction losses estimated using the Ergun equation (Hendry 2021).

Figure 2 Rotating Packed Bed design, (a) gas and liquid flows in an RPB, (b) sizing parameters for an RPB.

Trials using water and 30wt% MEA solutions at 1 ton per day scale found that the inner diameter was too small leading to carry over of MEA into the water wash, the minimum rotational speed was correct, the flooding correlation was accurate, and the pressure drop estimate was within 10% of measured values. The predicted outer diameter (1100mm) for 90% capture from a flue gas containing 12 vol% CO_2 was incorrect with a maximum of 76% capture being achieved. The reason for the under prediction was the use of data from a 300mm diameter RPB absorber where the entrance zone (Luo 2012) and fast reaction kinetics at low amine loadings led to an overestimate of the rate of CO_2 absorption in the 1 ton per day absorber.

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